

Exploring Patanjali's Yoga Sutras for the Essence of Happiness: A Holistic Approach

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Abstract

The pursuit of happiness has become increasingly elusive in the modern world, despite advancements in technology and access to various comforts. This abstract explores the reasons behind the growing unhappiness and the teachings of Patanjali Yoga Sutra as a means to attain happiness. The current generation is burdened by busy lifestyles, excessive workloads, materialistic desires, and imbalanced life style, leading to heightened stress levels and broken relationships. The root cause of unhappiness lies in restless desires and the fear of an uncertain future. Happiness is a state of mind, and it cannot be achieved through external material possessions. Pleasure, on the other hand, is the gratification of sensual desires and provides temporary satisfaction. The practice of yoga, as described in Patanjali Yoga Sutras, offers guidelines for happiness by transforming negativity into positivity and promoting physical, mental, and spiritual development. By integrating Patanjali's principles into daily life, an individual can experience positive transformation and attain happiness.

Introduction

Globally, technological advancement has changed the society, human being and their life style ever in the history of mankind. The present civilization came to the era of digitalization, where everything is accessible at the press of button. We are getting all kinds of facilities with the help of science and technology, such as computer, television, macro and micro machines, mobile phone, internet; multimedia, artificial intelligent etc. makes our life more comfortable [1]. Today, the social life is entirely dependent on science and technology. Hence, a greater number of advantages and facilities we consume to make our life happy and pleasurable [2]. However, the modern people so called the global generations are less happy today, despite having everything in life. Behind that it has a couple of reasons. In the modern world people are too busy with their works. They have no time to take care about their own health. Perhaps globalisation pushes the human being as a productive machine [3]. Consequently, people are running after the money and

material wealth, that tendency makes the mind restless too. Apart from that excessive workload, fostering inner desire, pursuing after the success, imbalance life style have been increased stress level among the people. Thus, the reason throughout the day people remains upset and they are not able to maintain the family life properly, for that reason their relationships also broken frequently. As per the World Happiness Report 2019, negative feeling, worry, sadness, and also anger have been increasing around the world, up to Twenty Seven percent (27%). Economist Jeffrey David Sachs said that "We are in an era of rising tensions and negative emotions". Reason may be that we are striving to get the happiness from material objects. Unlike others things material objects also have positive and negative impact on us. If the objects are favourable to us, we feel pleasure, if not then we feel pain. Moreover, our unending desire and never-ending expectation are the remarkable hindrance towards the happiness in life. Essentially, pleasure is a meaningful aspect of human being. It is the gratification of sensual desires. In fact, it

More Information

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is the satisfaction of senses and some extent to mind. Though, it is not everlasting phenomena. Pleasure is the feeling of pleasant emotions however; meaning involves a sense of fulfilment or purpose in life [4]. The very moment we achieved something, we felt pleasure and we are trying to be remain happy along with it. However, the value of achievement becomes less to us after getting any worldly objects or winning something. Simultaneously, on the other side gradually we begin too unhappy. Because, it is the human nature is to achieve more and more. Hence, desire and expectation has been increased day after day [5]. Men experiences pleasure from various way i.e., by travelling new places, watching sun set, rowing boat, playing a game, watching television, reading a book, singing a song, playing a musical instrument, gasping with friends or even consuming drugs and alcohol etc. pleasure can be either positive nor negative, but happiness is always positive in nature. Pleasure is dependent on a particular activity and it lasts only short period of time and ends after the action. The outside world is the source of enjoyment, but the inside is where happiness comes from.

Generally, happiness is a state of mind. It is not something that exists outside of the body. It is inside and within the body. You cannot be separated from your thinking. It is not an independent being from the body. It is a part and parcel of the body, not a separate entity. [6] state that happiness is "the experience of joy, contentment, or positive well-being, combined with a sense that one's life is good, meaningful, and worthwhile." Martin, Seligman explored three dimensions of happiness in 2002 and that can be cultivated namely, the pleasant life: it is associate with comes from experience of pleasantness [13]. The good life: it comes from the satisfying activities. At the end Seligman said the meaningful life: using one's capacity which is larger than oneself and make positive impact on the world.

Yoga is an ancient art based on scientific approach for the development of body, mind and spirit. Yoga was invented as a tool for acquiring the knowledge and wisdom as a means to become happier. Yoga is not merely a form of bodily exercise; it is an ancient technology for happiness and peaceful way of living [7]. Maharishi Patanjali elicited the Yoga Sutras; date back around 200 years B.C, as a way to understand the life by removing all kinds of afflictions [8]. Yoga and its amazing techniques help us to transform negativity into the positivity as to achieve a healthy and happy life. In-fact yoga is a wonderful tool for happiness. Presently the dose of yoga is open for all. Hence, everybody can enable to practice yogic skills and methods which have been prescribed in the Patanjali yoga sutras (PYS). Continue practice of yoga can change your life. Yoga is an ancient technology but the fruits of yoga are still

working efficiently and relevance to the modern people too.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the reasons behind the growing unhappiness and the teachings of Patanjali Yoga Sutra as a means to attain happiness.
2. To find the philosophically based practical solution to lead a happy life in this techno-electronics age.
3. To provide the knowledge of Yoga to achieve a happy and balance life.

Methods

In order to carry out this descriptive study, we thoroughly examined the important works that covered the Patanjali Yoga Sutras and explored their profound perspectives on happiness. Through a synthesis of the viewpoints presented in a number of highly influential books and articles, we sought to identify the ultimate secrets of happiness through the Patanjali Yoga Sutras. The aim of this study is to offer insights into achieving happiness based on Patanjali's Yoga Sutras, providing comprehensive and relevant information for the pursuit of happiness in modern world.

Happiness and Unhappiness

According to yoga sutras of Patanjali, happiness comes from the tranquillity of the mind. It is happened when the "Chitta" or mind stuff restrains itself from taking various forms, technically called as 'vrittis.' The mind has three different states, in yoga it is known as Tamasic, considering lethargic or idiotic mind. Rajasic, refers to the enjoyment or active state of mind. And sattvic, refers to the tranquillity or calmness state of mind. It comes after the cessation of 'Vrittis' (activity of mind). The calm man is the one who has experienced happiness. "Lord Buddha said that happiness is something which can be felt but cannot describe in words." The framework of Patanjali yoga sutras contained profound knowledge and worth to exploring for those who desire to achieve eternal happiness. Patanjali stated in the yoga sutra 1:3

तदा द्रष्टुः स्वरूपेऽवस्थानम् ॥१.३॥

Tada drashtuh svarupe avasthanam (PYS: 1: 3)

All at that time the seer (self) rest in its own state.

As soon as the thoughts have come to an end or cease, by the practice of Yoga the seer or soul identifies itself in its own unmodified state. Only then, one can understand the true nature of self, which is unchanging and felt eternal happiness indeed.

According to Patanjali's yoga sutras, unhappiness is a state that arises from the disturbances and afflictions of the mind. He mainly talked about the five kleshas or suffering which are the hindrance towards the happiness in life.

अविद्यास्मितारागद्वेषाभिनिवेशाः क्लेशाः ॥२.३॥
Avidya'smitaragadvesabhinivesah klesah (PYS: II: 3)
The five klesas (Sufferings) are ignorance, egoism,
attachment, aversion and fear of death.

Vyasa, in his commentary on yoga sutras said that this five false knowledge which binds us and restrain against the right knowledge or wisdom. Hence, ignorance is the primordial cause and later four kleshas are the consequence.

1. Avidya (Ignorance): Refers to lack of knowledge or vidya and it is the root cause of all sufferings. Often, we think that we are not a soul rather than a body. Hence, it is nothing but ignorance only.
2. Asmita (Egoism): refers to the identification with ego or the sense of "I", is a cause of unhappiness explained in the yoga sutras of Patanjali. Here we make ourselves limited.
3. Raga (Attachment): Attachment to the desires, material objects, relationships, is another cause of unhappiness.
4. Dvesha (Aversion): it refers to the opposite of attachment. It is the feeling of strong dislike or avoidance towards certain experiences, situations, or people. Once we resist or reject something, immediately it creates inner conflict.
5. Abhinivesah (Fear of death): It is also considered a root cause of suffering or unhappiness. When we are excessively attached to our physical existence and fear the uncertainty and impermanence of life, it can lead to anxiety, stress, and a constant sense of dissatisfaction.

Maharishi Patanjali had given the technique to eradicate the kleshas i.e., sufferings.

मैत्रीकरुणामुदितोपेक्षां सुखदुःखपुण्यापुण्यविषयाणां
 भावनातश्चित्तप्रसादनम् ॥१.३३॥

Maitri-karuna-muditopeksanam sukha-dukha- punya-
punya visayanam bhavanatschittaprasadanam. (PYS:I:
33).

By cultivating feelings of friendship, mercy, joy, and indifference towards happy, unhappy, good, and evil respectively, purify the mind (Chitta).

Patanjali talked about the four pillars of attitudes which help us to eradicate the sufferings and enable to bring happiness. These four pillars of attitudes are:

1. Maitree (Friendship): Patanjali state that we have to friendly towards someone who is looking happy. In order to achieve happiness, we must have friendship for all, it is an easy way. By adopting this behaviour an individual can feel a sense of happiness. But this also true that often we forget and behave opposite to the person who is happy. Instead to be friendly we feel sad and sorrow.

2. Karuna (Merciful): We must be merciful towards those who are in misery. Kindness and compassionate attitudes we must maintain throughout the life.

3. Mudita (Gladness): Feeling gladness, rejoicing in regard to the subjects who is good or virtuous.

4. Upekshanam (Indifference): Showing indifference in regard to the subject of wicked people who is involved in wrongful activity.

Further, Maharishi Patanjali expressing / addressing the way to cultivate positive attitudes.

वितर्कबाधने प्रतिपक्षभावनम् ॥२.३३॥

Vitarka-badhane prati-paksa-bhavanam (PYS: II: 33)

Prevent negative thoughts which are harmful to Yoga and contrary thoughts should be cultivated.

'Vitarka' (improper or discursive thoughts) is the term used by Maharishi Patanjali to draw the attention of the yogi or yoga practitioners to tackle the worse situation like negative thoughts inculcate to the mind. Human mind is ever fluctuating from one place to another. Hence, a positive and negative thought often comes in the mind throughout the day. As soon as the negative thought arises in (chitta) the mind time and again it gets (Badhane) binds or disturbs the mind. These forces drive away or bind us towards the negative thoughts and make us restless and unhappy. Patanjali state that when this situation comes in the mind immediately begin to think (Pratipaksha) the opposite thought as to alter of negative thought until unless you feel peace. This attitude gives the tremendous joy and happiness. Hence, cultivating the positive or proper thought is essential for achieving the happiness.

Further Maharishi Patanjali talked about the unconditional happiness and happiness is an attitude. In Patanjali Yoga sutra mentioned about Santosha (contentment, happiness). It is the second niyama in Ashtangayoga. This is one of the rules of yoga that cultivating the practice of being happy.

संतोषादनुत्तमसुखलाभः ॥२.४२॥

Santosha anuttamah sukhalahbah (PYS: II: 42)

From contentment, supreme happiness is gained

Essentially, the meaning of 'Santosh' is addressed by Patanjali as the satisfaction or contentment.

It is an attitude which can be cultivated through the practice of yoga. Contentment (Santosh) emphasizing on one's capacity or ability, positions (higher or lower levels) at workplace, surrounding material wealth, whatever the things possess in one's life must remain happy and have the blessings or feeling grateful for all those things which you have been still using in life. It is the human tendency that they never look at what they have; instead of that they always focus on what they

lack and what is still missing from their lives. Today's generation obsessed with materialistic happiness only. Hence, containment teaches us to remain happy under any circumstances in life. Once you develop this attitude you will be able to achieve (Anuttamah) the supreme happiness or the higher level of happiness. It is a feeling of mental satisfaction and deep inner peace. The fruits of satisfaction are the happiness or great joy. Self-satisfaction comes from the cleanliness of the negative thoughts, pet ideas, negativity, narrowness, prejudice, and preconceive notion. While receiving the immeasurable gift of happiness one has to remove all negativity from the mind and give effort to change the present situations of life. And make a balance between success and failure. As the life have its own rules, the experience of pain and sufferings and even the experience of joy and happiness.

Discussion

The study explores the modern problem of declining happiness in spite of material luxuries and technical breakthroughs. It painstakingly describes the many causes of the rising discontent in the contemporary world, highlighting the dangers of a fast-paced, materialistic way of life that breeds stress, strained relationships, and emotional instability. The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali are a fundamental resource for comprehending and obtaining bliss. The abstract artfully illustrates how Patanjali's teachings about the pursuit of happiness are inextricably tied to mental peace [9]. It highlights the contrast between the transient pleasure that comes from outside stimuli and the permanent contentment that comes from within by defining the distinctions between pleasure and happiness. An organised framework for understanding the barriers to happiness is provided by the identification of the five kleshas (sufferings) listed in Patanjali's sutras: ignorance, egoism, attachment, aversion, and fear of death. These kleshas, which are engrained in human nature, stand in the way of obtaining genuine happiness [10]. The abstract explains how Patanjali prescribes treating these kleshas by cultivating good thoughts and attitudes like friendship, mercy, happiness, and indifference. This insightful and pertinent discussion on mental training and emotional balance as means of achieving happiness is pertinent to the current state of society's pursuit of emotional stability. Furthermore, the idea of Santosha, or contentment, appears as a crucial component in the search for happiness. Patanjali's teachings offer a fundamental way to combat the never-ending need for more and promote inner serenity regardless of external circumstances by promoting an attitude of gratitude and contentment for one's current circumstances [11]. Combining these antiquated philosophical ideas with modern problems offers a comprehensive method for

comprehending and putting happiness-promoting techniques into practise.

Implications

The findings of this investigation have broad ramifications. In a society where tension, anxiety, and discontent are common, the understandings found in Patanjali's Yoga Sutras provide a path towards mental health and personal development [12].

Mindfulness in Contemporary Life: Applying the Yoga Sutras' teachings to day-to-day living can help people manage the stresses of contemporary life. These lessons can be used to develop mindfulness practises that reduce stress and improve mental toughness.

Relationships and Emotional Intelligence: Recognizing emotional patterns that impede personal development and damage relationships is made easier by an understanding of the kleshas. Through addressing these underlying issues, people can cultivate more robust relationships and emotional intelligence.

Change from Materialism to Contentment: Santosha's emphasis promotes a perspective change away from materialistic goals and toward discovering contentment within oneself. This change has the potential to redefine happiness and success and increase life satisfaction.

Promotion of Mental Health: By placing a strong emphasis on self-awareness and emotional control, Patanjali's teachings provide useful tools for boosting mental health, assisting in the prevention and management of mental health difficulties.

The research not only pinpoints the reasons for sadness but also provides practical remedies based on age-old knowledge. It heralds a way for long-lasting happiness in the modern world by promoting a paradigm shift towards inner contentment and emotional stability.

Conclusion

Pursuit of happiness is a fundamental aspect of human life. In this ever-changing innovative world people are looking happiness at the outside. Giving happiness to others is enormously vital to our own happiness. Since, the happiness comes from making others happy. Nobody likes misery in this world. At the same time, no one wants to remain unhappy. In the modern era of digitalization and technological advancement, people have access to numerous facilities and conveniences; still, they often find themselves less happy. The reasons behind this paradox are multifaceted. Excessive workload, materialistic pursuits, imbalanced lifestyles, and unending desires contribute to increased stress and unhappiness among individuals. Yoga, an ancient art and science, provides valuable tools for achieving happiness and transforming negativity into positivity. By understanding and applying the wisdom of ancient teachings like yoga, individuals can strive to attain genuine and lasting happiness in their lives.

Recommendation

Based on the study the following recommendations have been made; these are as follows:

1. Always have an intention to focus on the positive things and display positive attitude towards other living creatures.
2. Always keep smiling and be happy, it gives a positive vibration to others.
3. Avoid all negativity around you.
4. Regularly practice yoga and follow the yogic principles of Yama and Niyama.
5. Involve yourself in social activity and help needy people it will bring self satisfaction.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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